

Gender Equality
GE ACADEMY

D7.1 Dissemination, communication & stakeholders' engagement Strategy (VIL)

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Deliverable 7.1: Dissemination, communication & stakeholders' engagement Strategy

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1. Introduction

The GE Academy project aims at developing and implementing a high-quality capacity-building programme on gender equality in research, innovation and higher education. The capacity-building programme will be based on state-of-the-art knowledge and composed of a series of tailor-made training materials and different training formats (including: Physical Trainings, Summer Schools, Physical Interactive workshops, Webinars, Distributive Open Collaborative Courses (DOCCs), Train-the-Trainer sessions) and it will be executed in at least 15 countries. At the same time, a pan-European network of gender trainers, both female and male, will be established so as to train, practitioners and researchers will be trained, coached and upskilled for delivering gender training sessions tailored to the R&I and HE communities all over Europe and beyond.¹

In this respect, key for the achievement of the ambitious objectives of GE Academy is the implementation of a highly effective dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy that will ensure:

- The wider promotion and outreach of the project to critical stakeholders to speed up its wider use and impact to the economy and the society.
- The communication of the benefits and opportunities offered through our programmes and activities.
- The engagement and involvement of key stakeholders in the project's activities.
- The development and sustainability of the overall project and the pan-European network of gender trainers and other relevant stakeholders.
- The exploitation of the project results and the sustainability of the proposed activities and overall approach.

This deliverable provides an overview of the project's dissemination and communication strategy focusing on the project's target groups, the development of appropriate communication messages, the dissemination channels and tools that are used and will be used as well as the planning and monitoring procedures to ensure the quality and effectiveness of the communication activities. This plan will be reviewed and updated on a regular basis for assessing new and possible dissemination opportunities that would emerge during the course of the project.

1.1 Document Structure

This document is organized in the following sections: It begins with a presentation of the overall dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy of the project highlighting its main phases and elements. It is followed by the description of the project's communication tools, channels and

¹ GE Academy Grant Agreement

tactics. Then, it presents the project's activities with the numbers associated with them to track, monitor and assess the progress.

2. Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy

Communication and dissemination in GE Academy is targeted at raising awareness of the project, reaching the target audiences and maximising the outreach of the project activities and results thereby contributing to tackle issues of gender equality in research institutions and research teams through structural change, and issues of gender dimension into research contents, following the three main ERA objectives set for gender equality in research.

The target is to ensure that information is shared with appropriate audiences on a timely basis and by the most effective means and to prepare the ground for ensuring sustainability after its completion by finding potential collaborators to ensure the optimal use of GE Academy results and speed up the potential of their wider use and impact to the economy and society.

Therefore, emphasis is given at the project's dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy in order to provide clear guidelines for all the communication activities including all operational elements of dissemination and thus ensure that project results will be disseminated to reach relevant target groups with appropriate content and on time.

To this end the core elements that formulate the communication strategy of GE Academy are the objectives, target groups, key messages, channels and methods, timing and evaluation.

Figure 1. Dissemination and communication strategy

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Communication activities will transition between three different phases; the first phase will roughly cover the first 6 months of the project when proper planning will be organised and a strong community needs to be built. Therefore, the first phase includes preparatory activities such as to identify and approach the target audiences, develop dissemination material and create the initial content.

The second phase will cover the remaining M7-M18, when the objective of the project turns to promoting its activities to a wide audience to ensure participation, not only to attract even more and better participants, but to maximise the impact to all participants. During this phase, we will target at more specific networking with other projects (e.g. all SwafS GEPs projects, ACT, SAGE, GENERA, etc.) and participation in third-party events to ensure the wider dissemination of our activities to the most relevant audience. In parallel, this is the phase when the establishment of the community of stakeholders and trainers network will be intensified to reach its high potential.

Finally, the third phase (M19-M36) will continue the dissemination and communication of project activities via its channels given more specific on social media campaigns for the capacity-building activities and on the sustainability of its community of stakeholders and the pan-European network of trainers.

The two common targets of the third phases will include the systematic use of a variety of dissemination activities to reach and involve the target audience groups and the integration of knowledge coming from relevant support actions and projects.

2.1 Key Target groups and Communication messages

The Dissemination and communication strategy in GE Academy draws upon target group needs and interests in order to define the communication goals for each subgroup and employ the most effective communication means to reach them. To this end, the following two figures present the project's primary and secondary target groups, while the table below presents our offer and the key messages to approach them.

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Image 1. Primary target groups of GE Academy

Target groups are on the one hand the experts and gender trainers, that will be trained themselves and engaged for the different tasks and requests. On the other hand, practitioners, researchers and trainers will profit from the knowledge and be able to implement the knowledge in their activities.

Image 2. Secondary target groups of GE Academy project

The principle guidelines for the development of the project's key messages are:

- To be clear, simple and easy to understand. The language should be appropriate for the target groups.
- To be tailored to the target groups; it is very important to carefully consider what they should know about the project. Avoid sending the same messages to different target groups. Each time revise the relevance of the message to the target groups.
- Provide correct and realistic information. Don't promise something that the project cannot offer in order to attract your target audiences.
- Encourage longer term participation (i.e. be part of the GE Academy community and network beyond the end of the project or each activity).

Based on these principles the table below presents an indicative list of communication messages that have been defined for the different target groups. A careful coordination among partners who act as spokespersons or information sources for the project is essential in order to avoid inconsistencies that may negatively affect the achievement of the project's broader goals.

Stakeholder category	Offer	Communication message
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Gender experts and trainers	Train-the-trainers trainings for the development of new skills	Further develop skills
HR Professionals & Research Performing Organisations middle management	Training to integrate the gender dimension in their organisations	Integration and establishment of gender-sensitive and fair recruitment and career management processes in organisations
Researchers	Training to integrate the gender dimension in their research and deepening their understanding of gender issues in R&I	Change of attitude towards gender to determine gender culture of academic and other research institutions and integrate the gender dimension in their research fields
Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)	Recommendations for influencing the internal policies and practices of the organisations towards gender equality	Influence the practices towards how sex and gender differences influence the trajectory of gender equality in their organisations
Research funding organisations (RFOs) & Policy makers (especially Ministries of Education)	Recommendations for supporting and strengthening the environment for valuing gender dimension in research content and innovation / Initiatives for the inclusion of gender equality perspective in research teams and the participation of women in decision-making in public universities and R&I organisations	Strengthen the environment for valuing gender dimension in research and innovation to foster innovation and participation of women in decision making
Other EU-wide networks & initiatives	Offering project results and supporting dissemination activities	Highlight the importance of collaborations for better and higher quality results in research and support in dissemination activities
Editors of scientific journals	Awareness raising to highlight the importance of incorporating gender perspectives in academic journals and publications	Highlight the impact of incorporating the gender perspective

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General audience (Including students)	Awareness raising	Highlight the importance of the integration of the gender dimension in R&I and HE
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Table 1. Communication Messages per target group

2.2 Communication tools and channels

The project will use both online and offline channels for its dissemination and communication activities.

Online channels: The following online channels will be used for the communication and dissemination of information on the implementation of the project, its activities and its results: GE Academy will use the project website, partners' websites with reference to the link of the initial site of the project, mailing lists, newsletters, online meetings, webinars, social media that will be used to raise awareness and enhance the participation in the project activities. A systematic approach and a further analysis have been made on the following chapter about the communication tools.

Offline channels: The following offline channels will be exploited for dissemination and communication activities so as to reach out all the target stakeholders and audience: logo, brochure, press releases, seminars, workshops, academic papers, conferences, raising awareness events and workshops.

Overall, GE Academy will capitalize on the networks of its consortium to multiply its reach. At local/national, European and international level all partners will be involved and engaged to increase the dissemination process and communicate the project to the respective stakeholders. GE Academy will establish new synergies with existing initiatives and projects (e.g. GenPORT, Eurogender, ACT Community of Practice, etc.) and other networks to exchange ideas and increase mutual learning. The communication channels and its tools will help communicate the project messages to each stakeholder category.

2.2.1 Project branding and visual identity

In order to create a single visual identity for the project and make it easily identifiable by the target audiences, all project material developed and to be developed include in prominent position the EU Funding visibility and the project logo.

The branding pack prepared by ViLabs to be used by all project members includes:

- Project Logo
- Brand guide
- PPT & Word templates (presentations, deliverables, minutes)
- Social media templates

And this package will also include other material that will be decided with partners during the second Consortium meeting in Paris in view of the trainings programme. This can include:

- GE Academy Poster

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- GE Academy Leaflet

Image 3. Standard template for all project presentations

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Image 4. Standard deliverable template

Image 5. Standard image with Consortium partners

GE Academy has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780738.

Image 6. Standard image with EU funding details

Image 7. Standard dimensions for social media channels created with Canva

2.2.2 Project website

The project website is one of the main sources of information about the project available to all stakeholders. It is the main communication tool of the project, especially in relation to fostering participation for the main project activities, the gender trainings. In particular, the GE Academy website aims at:

- Providing information about the project and help stakeholders understand the reasons to get involved and how they can participate in the project's activities.
- Directing potential participants to the different gender trainings and available opportunities.
- Providing a common reference for interested stakeholders to all the content produced.

The project's website is available at: <https://ge-academy.eu/>

The website was established immediately at the start of the project (M2) and will be maintained for at least two years after the project ends. The following figure presents the first general layout of the website homepage and the main sections that were part of it.

Figure 2. GE Academy website – Homepage

The main sections of the website are:

- **Homepage** (<https://ge-academy.eu/>): This page provides a brief and direct message for the wider public and those interested to gender equality, so they are motivated check more information about the project. It also includes the main website menu bar and presents in a dynamic way the latest news including the live Twitter feed, while the Consortium members are visible in the "Team" section. Finally, it showcases the project social media channels, the subscription to the

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project's newsletter list and it has the European Commission and the standard funding text in a prominent position.

- **About** (<https://ge-academy.eu/the-project/>): If someone clicks on menu for the about option then 5 options appear; the project, partners, advisory board, resources and contact us. This is the menu where you can find more information about the project, what it is, the organisations behind it, details to get connected with it and available resources, including project deliverables, press releases, and synergies with other projects.
- **Gender trainings** (<https://ge-academy.eu/gender-trainings/>): This section is mainly dedicated to provide information about what gender trainings are, who they are for, how you can apply, etc. This page will include direct links to another page which will be called calendar and it will be developed at a later stage, when the trainings will be kicked off. It will act as a key entry point of information and it will be highlighted in the homepage.
- **Get involved** (<https://ge-academy.eu/get-involved/>): This section is mainly dedicated to the primary target group of the project. It is acting as an information point for those willing to investigate options to get involved in the project activities.
- **News** (<https://ge-academy.eu/news/>): This page links all dynamic information related to the news and events of the project into one space.

To acknowledge the EU funding, the following sentence is provided together with the EU flag: "GE Academy has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780738."

About the website design, the current layout delivers a comprehensive structure, yet with a good accessibility. Each page on the website features the project logo. There a few more features on the website:

- **Searching inside the website:** Advanced website search engine.
- **Social sharing:** In every page, event and news, there is the capability of sharing this entry on social media. The functionality is simple and using the latest APIs (application program interface) of each social network being used. One click is enough, and the user can share the experience with its social-friends. The social networks that are being supported are the following ones: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn.
- **Security:** The security issue is the first that was taken into account when we were building this website. Brute force attacks, hacks on retrieving usernames, hacks on logins etc. are blocked. Plus, there is a software firewall running behind the website for preventing "suspicious" IPs from accessing the website. The identification of the "suspicious" IPs is being done automatically; "suspicious" actions are also being logged. Vulnerabilities that exist in other websites have been extinguished. Security section is being updated in an ongoing basis.
- **Search Engine Optimization (SEO):** The specific website is SEO friendly and after a period of time, google results will bring the website to higher ranking, which does not only depend of the website itself, back-links must be also included from other websites, e.g. partner websites, links on social medias etc. This procedure is a 2-way procedure.
- **User Interface (UI) – Appearance of the website:** The website is mobile friendly, tested also with google mobile friendly tool (this also push-ups our website on the google results).

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In order to assess how well the website is reaching stakeholders and acting as a source of information, the website uses standard web traffic analysis tools to track the number of visitors and similar metrics over the life of the project. The website will be continuously updated throughout the course of the project, and thus will act as a dynamic and up-to-date source of information for stakeholders. The website will stay up for two (2) years after the project end and VIL will be responsible for its updates and maintenance.

2.2.3 Social Media Channels

Social media channels are an integral part of our dissemination and communication strategy as they provide the chance to get connected and reach regions and stakeholders all over the world. The aim of this section is to present the basic elements of the social media strategy and its channels that will be used for the project. Our overall approach was based on the figure below, which represents our specific strategy using social media as a modern tool, which is constantly updated with news changes and features, to help us promote the project and its activities by adapting our communication messages to any given new features and explore new possibilities for reaching relevant audience.

Figure 3. Social media strategy of GE Academy

The channels were carefully chosen by ViLabs and they were presented to the Consortium during the kick-off meeting to finalise the decision and the targeting based on the partners experience from their individual accounts and networks. The following table was developed as initial thoughts before setting up the accounts and it was discussed as a basis with the Consortium:

Channel	Rationale	Frequency of posts
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most popular network; • Most of the partners maintain Facebook pages which can provide us our first audience; • Many features to capitalize on including video posting, events, photos, carousels, promoting the open calls in different ways without a limitation in characters; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post twice a week • More if the available content is critical;

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is the option to use advertisements to promote the page and the open calls; 	
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A popular network with short and concise messages; • Easy to use; • Many projects & relevant stakeholders use it; • Project partners have accounts with many followers and dedicated audience; • Based on past experience, Twitter is a successful tool for projects; • Helps to live blogging during events; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Almost in a daily basis, depending on the content. • Two tweets per week, if there is no occasion.
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add useful content e.g. articles, public calls, etc. • Tag the trainings' participants so they are able to share the news with their professional network; • Closed LinkedIn group with invitations only for the alumni members to motivate the community; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When an occasion to motivate the business network presents itself; • At least one post per two weeks
YouTube channel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful to share the project videos; • No wide dissemination of the channel per se, but of the individual videos; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When a video is available;

Table 2. Selection of the appropriate social media channels

Facebook Page

GE Academy has a Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/GEAcademy.eu/>), which currently counts 226 likes. The project logo was used as a profile image as well as the full name of the project is on the cover photo.

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Figure 4. GE Academy's Facebook Page

Twitter Profile

The Twitter account (https://twitter.com/GEAcademy_eu), which currently has 162 followers will be mainly used to promote the open calls and for live blogging all the sessions during our on-site activities. It is a great tool to connect with the most of our relevant stakeholder, which have already established a strong presence and they are very enthusiastic about our tweets. A screenshot below presents the Twitter profile with the logo on the profile image and a tailored cover page, which showcases our aim. Another important element is the text “about” with the following message “#genderequality academy & dissemination of gender knowledge across Europe. Funded @EU_H2020 project EU Official hashtag: #GEAcademy”, which contains a lot of relevant hash tags and tags the Horizon2020 Twitter account. GE academy goes by @GEAcademy_eu as a brand name for Twitter when our supporters want to tag us in relevant tweets.

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Figure 5. GE Academy's Twitter account

Two very important features to use on Twitter are the moments, which accumulate and present all the tweets from our profile and from accounts tagging us and present them in a consistent manner, so participants and interested audience are able to go back and check our activities. The other important feature is the Twitter lists, which we use in public and private mode; public mode to showcase friends and relevant accounts and give people the chance to subscribe to the lists and check the latest updates; private to accumulate the participants accounts of on-site activities, so when someone is posting can easily track the accounts to tag or the relevant tweets to retweet and keep in the loop with what those participants are doing after the on-site activities.

LinkedIn Page

LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/ge-academy/>) has a dual purpose for GE Academy. It is mainly used to promote professional content and to promote the project activities, but it is also used to motivate and accumulate the GE Academy alumni together in a group to help them stay in touch with each other and also connect with other members of the community; and give them a space to share any news and initiatives with the group.

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Figure 6. GE Academy's LinkedIn page

2.2.4 Newsletters and Press releases

Newsletters and Press Releases are to inform the public about the project's progress and to raise further awareness. Online tools are ideal for engaging a great number of stakeholders but more traditional tools are suitable for reaching all the categories and especially the community. A press release is more formal and aiming at being released in national or European newspapers. GE Academy project will publish frequently short and concise texts to disseminate through mailing lists and database lists in order to keep the audience informed and will be issued in a regular basis in order to announce and report about GE Academy's activities and findings. At least one newsletter will be produced every 6 months starting from June 2019 and this number can be increased based on the information to be sent to relevant stakeholders. Also, the topics could include key actions of the project taken (e.g. questionnaire sent out, meeting held etc.), key workshops/events/conferences/exhibitions where GE Academy has been presented or has organised, news about relevant projects, activities and events. All versions of the Newsletters will be prepared in English and distributed electronically through mailchimp. An initial template is ready and can be found in the figure below. GE Academy project will prepare press releases to raise awareness and disseminate information about the project. Press releases will be prepared for important project events or relevant milestones. Press releases will be published on the website, on social media channels and through press contacts of the partner organizations (in translation where necessary).

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Figure 7. Template for GE Academy's newsletters

2.2.5 Other communication tactics

Promotion through partners' online accounts

Partners are communicating the project and its activities through their online business accounts and networks, while their also using their individual accounts. The table below indicates the partner channels for promotion and outreach purposes. This table is not exhaustive, and it is regularly updated.

ViLabs (VIL)		Yellow Window (YW)		Knowledge and Innovation (K&I)	
Facebook	315 likes	Facebook	1410 likes	Website	N/A
Twitter	260 followers	Twitter	128 followers		
LinkedIn	103 followers	LinkedIn	496 followers		
Website	N/A	Instagram	99 followers		
		Website	N/A		
Institute of Sociology of the Academy of Sciences (ISAS)		Smart Venice (SV)		Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin (UMB)	
Facebook	2926 likes	Facebook	136 likes	Facebook	10507 likes
Twitter	930 followers	Website	N/A	Twitter	2089 followers
LinkedIn	82 followers			Website	N/A
Website	N/A				

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Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)		Büro für nachhaltige Kompetenz (B-NK)		Technological University Dublin (DIT)	
Facebook	31244 likes	Facebook	351 likes	Facebook	40325 likes
Twitter	39100 followers	LinkedIn	33 followers	Twitter	18500 followers
Instagram	3665 followers	Website	N/A	Instagram	4972 followers
Website	N/A			Website	N/A
Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)		Central European University (CEU)		K-RCN	
Facebook	174747 likes	Facebook	50231 likes	Facebook	1268 likes
Twitter	132900 followers	Twitter	9703 followers	Twitter	(English page) / 4206
Instagram	31800 followers	LinkedIn	19548 followers	Instagram	(Norwegian page)
Website	N/A	Instagram	3574 followers	Website	1034 followers
		Website	N/A		(English account) / 4309 followers
					(Norwegian account)
					768 followers
					N/A

Table 3. Social media in numbers per partner organization (access: 19/05/19)

Promotion through word of mouth

Word of mouth should never be underestimated as an old communication tactic. It is proven to be very effective during the course of the project. Partners are the ambassadors of the project and they speak and promote its activities at any given moment. For this reason, apart from the offline printed material, we will develop tailored presentations for each stakeholder category and for different occasions that will be available to partners on the shared Google Drive folder. The links will be kept private due to data protection issues. In addition, word of mouth plays a vital role on the applications for the gender training programmes as most of them are likely to be referred by a consortium partner, which means that individual emails and invitations are important for the success of the attempt to approach potential participants and relevant stakeholders. Moreover, partners have committed to attend relevant third-party events and relevant occasions to present and promote the project.

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Alumni participants and other relevant key players who got involved with the project activities will also act as ambassadors of the project and its activities. Their testimonials will be used on the project website and other communication material to highlight the quality of the capacity building programme.

Synergies with other projects and EU wide networks

The aim of this communication tactic is to plan and implement joint activities with external projects, initiatives, networks and communities. This can be facilitated through various channels including the project website, but also the links of the partners that are part of several consortia and networks. In order to understand if a synergy is useful, the GE Academy project needs to recognise the complementarities with other projects and identify a common purpose so these contacts and interactions will strengthen the outreach of the project and maximise the mobilisation of stakeholders.

The creation of synergies will be enabled by the promotion of information exchange with other initiatives, strengthening each other's communication efforts by relaying messages and the cross-promotion of results. GE Academy has already established contacts with the past projects and the new and its partners have decided to invite each other in events and conferences for sharing their expertise.

GE Academy is a proud member of Eurogender (<https://eurogender.eige.europa.eu/users/gender-equality-academy>) (powered by the European Institute of Gender Equality (EIGE), an online consultation and cooperation platform) and GenPORT (<https://www.genderportal.eu/projects/gender-equality-academy>) (a developing online community of practitioners, policy makers and researchers is served by the GenPORT portal, and made up of organisations and individuals working across the globe for gender equality and excellence in science, technology and innovation)

The screenshot displays the user interface of the Gender Equality Academy website. On the left, a navigation sidebar includes links for HOME, WORKSPACES, ONLINE DISCUSSIONS, YOUR DOCUMENTS, AREAS OF INTEREST, LATEST POSTS, EVENTS, SURVEYS, and COMMUNITY. The main content area features a header with the EuroGender logo and a search bar. Below the header, the title 'Gender Equality Academy' is prominently displayed. A section titled 'Areas of Interest' lists several key areas: Gender Mainstreaming Methods & Tools, Gender Statistics & GE Index, Institutional Mechanisms, International Cooperation & Development, Research & Innovation, and Science. A 'Workspaces' section highlights the 'European Network of Women in Digital (EWID)'. On the right side, contact information for the academy is provided, including its location in Greece, Thessaloniki, and social media links for Website, Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. The footer contains copyright information for EuroGender and links to 'About EuroGender', 'Contact Us', 'Video Tutorials', 'Disclaimer', and 'Data protection'.

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Figure 8. GE Academy on Eurogender

The screenshot shows the GenPORT website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with a 'Help' icon, a user profile for 'Vasia Madasi (76 points)', a 'User menu' dropdown, and an 'Add content' button. Below this is the GenPORT logo and a main navigation menu with links for 'Resources', 'Projects', 'Events', 'Organisations', 'People', 'Groups', 'Blog', and 'Policy&Law'. A search bar is located on the right side of the navigation menu.

Gender Equality Academy

View Edit

About (English version):
GE Academy is an Horizon 2020 project which aims to develop and implement a high-quality capacity-building programme on gender equality in research, innovation and higher education.

URL: <https://ge-academy.eu/>

Acronym: GE Academy

Dates: Tuesday, January 1, 2019 to Friday, December 31, 2021

Twitter: [Twitter](#)

Facebook: [Facebook](#)

LinkedIn: [LinkedIn](#)

Contact Email: info@ge-academy.eu

Type of Project: EU, H2020

Type of policy or practical measure:
Career development, Structural change, Quotas, Targets, Gender Budgeting, Equality officers & gender equality plans, Mainstreaming mechanisms, Human resources management, Work-life balance, Awareness raising

Scientific discipline:
Natural sciences, Engineering and technology, Medical and health sciences, Social sciences, Humanities

Gender and Science taxonomy:
[Research content and knowledge production](#) [Institutional practices](#)

The banner image features the text 'Gender Equality GE ACADEMY' at the top. Below the text, two individuals are shown sitting at a table, looking at and discussing documents. The image includes a 'Learn more' button and a 'Get involved' button. The 'pagepeeker' logo is visible in the bottom right corner of the banner.

Figure 9. GE Academy on GenPORT

3. Monitoring, evaluation and progress

This dissemination and communication plan and the impact of its activities will be regularly assessed during the course of the project. The quality and the impact of those activities will be measured through quantitative and qualitative indicators. The tables below present the indicators of the project that have been sourced from the project DoA to measure the success of the project in communication terms.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Target value	Target value (M24)	Target value (M36)	Means of measurement
Number of accesses per year	>2000 accesses per year	N/A	N/A	Google Analytics
Number of downloads of deliverables	N/A	N/A	>300 downloads	Website metrics
Number of individuals signed up to receive email updates on project progress	N/A	>150 individuals/ organisations	>300 individuals/ organisations	Mailchimp metrics
Number of organisations signed up to receive email updates on project progress	N/A			

Table 4. KPIs linked with the project website

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Target value (M24)	Target value (M36)	Means of measurement
Number of Twitter followers	N/A	600	Twitter analytics
Number of Facebook likes	N/A	400	Facebook page insights
Number of project videos	N/A	5	Uploaded on the GE Academy YouTube channel
Number of YouTube video views	N/A	200 per video	YouTube analytics

Deliverable 7.1: Dissemination, communication & stakeholders' engagement Strategy

Table 5. KPIs linked with social media channels

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Target value (M36)	Means of measurement
Number of manuscripts accepted for publication	>2 publications	Letter of acceptance
Number of policy briefs / white papers	>2 policy briefs / white papers	Publicly available on the project website
Public awareness and sharing of experience with external experts in the field	> 10 participations in conferences and workshops	Pictures / agendas, etc.
Number of leaflets distributed	Distribution of at least 500 leaflets	Number of copies produced per partner / Pictures of the leaflet distributed in events

Table 6. Other dissemination metrics

The dissemination and communication strategy was drafted from the beginning of the project and it is continuously updated according to project activities and relevant requirements. The dissemination plan will be regularly assessed during the course of the project. To allow an adequate monitoring of the external communication activities and understand the impact generated by these activities, partners are requested to register the activities and actions carried out (Annex I) in a monthly basis.

Annex I: Dissemination and communication activities reporting template

Dissemination reporting

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Dissemination reporting

1. How to complete the dissemination reporting

Every partner should report its implementing dissemination activities using this template. According to the Participant's part of the SA, dissemination activities include:

- Organisation of a Conference
- Organisation of a Workshop or a Networking event
- Press release: A press release is a written communication directed at members of the news media (e.g. journalists, bloggers, etc.) for the purpose of announcing something about the project.
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publications: Organizational publications, and other written articles in conference proceedings, articles in special journal issues, blogs, where authors are invited to contribute because they are well known for their expertise.
- Exhibition
- Flyer
- Training
- Social Media
- Website
- Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)
- Participation to a Conference
- Participation to a Workshop or a Networking event
- Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop
- Video/Film
- Trade Fair
- Participation to activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects
- Other (e.g. peer reviewed publications, Newsletters)

This document is an overview report. The IRW leader will use this document to order to:

- Lead the project website with information about the reported activities
- Show the reported information through the project social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.)
- Analysed the information to extract conclusions and statistics that will publish on a frequent basis to the consortium in order to monitor the progress and take any mitigating actions if needed.

This document should be updated in a monthly basis (until the last working day). You may complete this document and control the IRW leader (Email: irw@ec.europa.eu)

To report your activities, follow the steps below:

- Check the Table of Contents and click on the category that best describes the implemented activity.
- Complete the activity by filling out the respective table.

Dissemination reporting

2. Organisation of a conference

Title/Tagline for this activity

Conference title	
Conference website	
Title	
Location/Venue	City, Country
Participating IRW(s)	
IRW leader partner(s)	
Other contact(s)	

Type of audience reached

Please, select more than one type (ONLY if applicable, up to a maximum of 8. Please, indicate ESTIMATED no. of persons reached per type of audience (if required).

Audience	Individuals	EU Society	Policy Makers	Media	Scientists	Customers	Other
Scientific Community (e.g. peer-reviewed journals)	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number

Please, copy below any photos or copy relevant texts (e.g. to website, presentation files, brochures, newsletters, etc.)

Comments

Would you like to report any information about the outcome of the activity in relation to IRW Academy's benefit?

Dissemination reporting

3. Organisation of a Workshop/Networking event

Title/Tagline for this activity

Workshop title	
Workshop website	
Title	
Location/Venue	City, Country
Participating IRW(s)	
IRW leader partner(s)	
Other contact(s)	

Type of audience reached

Please, select more than one type (ONLY if applicable, up to a maximum of 8. Please, indicate ESTIMATED no. of persons reached per type of audience (if required).

Audience	Individuals	EU Society	Policy Makers	Media	Scientists	Customers	Other
Scientific Community (e.g. peer-reviewed journals)	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number

Please, copy below any photos or copy relevant texts (e.g. to website, presentation files, brochures, newsletters, etc.)

Comments

Would you like to report any information about the outcome of the activity in relation to IRW Academy's benefit?

Dissemination reporting

4. Press release

Title/Tagline for this activity

Conference title	
Conference website	
Title	
Location/Venue	City, Country
Participating IRW(s)	
IRW leader partner(s)	
Other contact(s)	

Type of audience reached

Please, select more than one type (ONLY if applicable, up to a maximum of 8. Please, indicate ESTIMATED no. of persons reached per type of audience (if required).

Audience	Individuals	EU Society	Policy Makers	Media	Scientists	Customers	Other
Scientific Community (e.g. peer-reviewed journals)	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number

Please, copy below any photos or copy relevant texts (e.g. to website, presentation files, brochures, newsletters, etc.)

Comments

Would you like to report any information about the outcome of the activity in relation to IRW Academy's benefit?